

Sampling protocol for water sampling for quality assessment by project participants

English version (for ACTION reviewing purposes)

Aim

This protocol includes orientation for the water sampling task by the “Water sentinels” project participants (CS). These samples will be used to provide information on the location of possible water pollution events, which are expected to be observed by the project participants at Sado estuary. Water samples will be collected in April – June 2021, and will be analyzed by researchers of Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (IPS).

First draft: 08/04/2021

Last revision: 14/05/2021

Authors: Ana Mata, Paula Chainho, Raquel Gaspar, Ricardo Salgado, Sílvia Tavares

Participants (5) will be recruited by Raquel Gaspar on the Sado estuary fishing community (Carrasqueira e Faralhão). To participate, they will be informed about the activities to be performed and the personal data privacy, through the delivery of a consent document. Participation is voluntary. For the training, they will receive a sampling kit, which they will be responsible to maintain. First sampling activity of each participant will be guided by Raquel Gaspar. The transport of the water samples from the sampling locations to IPS must be made as soon as possible after collection, up to a maximum of 24h. Samples transport logistics will be coordinated by Ocean Alive. Samples temperature during transport must be kept low, which is especially relevant on hot days: this will be assured by using a cooler bag and frozen plates with the samples, and maintaining them sheltered from direct light/sun direct exposure.

Each sampling kit will include:

- 1 GPS
- 1 plate or sheet for data record
- 4 plastic water bottle (5L) (1 for sample)
- 3 cooler bag (1 for sample)
- 1 secchi disc
- 1 thermometer
- 1 plastic jar mounted on an extensible stick

The total number of samples to be collected is 20. From these, we aim for 15 to represent pollution events and 5 to be “blanks” (water samples collected on the locations where they are used to see signs of water pollution, but on a day when no signs of it are present). Each participant will collect 4 water samples.

The first sample to be collected by each participant is the “blank”.

In resume: 20 water sampling events will be made by 5 participants. So, each one of the participants will collect 4 samples ($5 \times 4 = 20$). Each of the participants will collect (if possible) 1 reference and 3 test samples. So, for the total 20 samples collected, we expect 5 references and 15 test samples.

These are the characteristics of water pollution events which participants should look for:

- An abnormal water flow, different of the water body; a current which go against the normal water flow
- “Strange things” observed the water surface: foams, oils
- Water patches with different colour, transparency, smell
- Higher temperature of the water
- More turbidity than usual
- Identification of a suspect water source (such as a stream)

When a pollution event is detected, the participants must use the following procedure:

1. Navigate at low velocity; turn-off the engine and/or anchor the boat when possible (according to all the navigation safety measures). Keep the sampling water area as undisturbed as possible; contamination of the sample may occur mainly due to two factors:
 - a) Water is mixed with sediment due to the boat movement or human stepping on the nearby area and/or
 - b) Boat propeller and/or engine pass through the water to be sampled;
2. Begin data collection, choosing the least disturbed water areas around the boat (usually on the prow of the boat);
3. Start by measuring water turbidity using the secchi disc method (*see method description below**), always when the location depth allows it; register data on the plate;
4. Rinse water collection material (plastic jar and bottle) twice with estuary water before start the water collection;
5. Start water collection; use the extensible stick and plastic jar to collect water from the identified place where characteristics suggest pollution:
 - a. If from the boat (higher depth): depending upon the characteristics shown, sample shall be collected between the surface (e.g. foams, oils) or until 50 cm deep (e.g. water treatment facilities, where the emissary is closer to the bottom);
 - b. If by feet (lower depth, streams or creeks): be carefull, the plastic jar must never touch the sediment; always wait for the fine sediment to settle as much as possible, to avoid contamination; use the plastic jar on the extensible cable to obtain the sample as close to the pollution source as possible.
6. Fill the plastic bottle container (5L) as much as possible, until it spills out; close it;
7. Measure water temperature using the thermometer; register in the plate
8. Write on the sample tag the date + first letters of the first and last name of the collector;
9. Accomodate the water sample inside the cooler bag and try to keep it as fresh as possible (at shadow, or even tie a cable on it and put it in the water when the boat is not navigating);
10. Mark the position on the GPS; register the point number on the plate;
11. Register on the plate date + hour + collector name initial letters + other aspects noticed (colour, smell, turbidity, others); if possible/relevant take a picture of the water to share with Ocean Alive team;

12. Call Ocean Alive team as soon as possible to tell about the collection data and prepare logistics for the sample transport to IPS.

***Measure turbidity with secchi disc methodology**

Preliminary remarks:

- measurement should be made on the shadow side of the boat, to minimize error due to light reflection on water surface;
- if the boat is anchored prior to the measurement, be sure it did not cause bottom sediment resuspension on the measurement location;
- secchi disc must be put down and read on the horizontal position; if it is windy or there is current, add weight to the disc, to be sure it is read on the horizontal position;
- [optional] be careful to not throw the secchi disc at the sea and miss the cable; if available, add a buoy to the cable end, so it can be found and recovered in the case if cable slips out of the hands

How to measure:

1. Let the disc enter slowly at the water, by losing the cable and letting the disc go down, until the black and white pattern is no longer distinguishable; read the depth on the cable and register it as "depth 1";
2. Loose more cable and let the disc do down 1 meter further; after, start to pull the disc up slowly, until the black and white pattern is visible again; read this depth in the cable and register it as "depth 2";
3. Secchi depth will be obtained by calculating the average between depths 1 and 2.